

PREPARATION OF ARBUDAHARA RASA: A PHARMACEUTICAL PERSPECTIVE**Dr. Rubina B. S.^{1*}, Dr. Sangeeta Rao², Dr. Vikram S.³, Dr. Yashwant⁴**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Arbudahara Rasa is a classical mercurial formulation mentioned in Rasaratna Samuccaya and indicated in Arbuda and related disorders. The formulation contains Shuddha Parada processed with Tanduliyaka, Varshabhu, Tambula, Kumari, Bala, and Gomutra through repeated Bhavana followed by Puta. Scientific documentation of its pharmaceutical preparation is essential for reproducibility and standardization. **Aim:** To prepare Arbudahara Rasa according to the classical reference and document the pharmaceutical procedures, observations, and yield. **Materials and Methods:** Shodhana of Ashuddha Parada was carried out by Urdhwapatana using Haridra Churna and Kumari Swarasa. The obtained Shuddha Parada was subjected to sequential Bhavana with Tanduliyaka Swarasa, Varshabhu Kwatha, Tambula Swarasa, Kumari Swarasa, Bala Moola Kwatha, and Gomutra. A second cycle of Bhavana was repeated to attain complete homogenization. Chakrikas prepared from the final Kalka were subjected to various Puta trials including Laghu Puta, Gorvara Puta, and Muffle Furnace Puta. **Results:** From 750 g of Ashuddha Parada, 665 g of Shuddha Parada was obtained with a yield of 91.06%. Repeated Bhavana resulted in a homogeneous Kalka without visible mercury globules. Initial Laghu Puta trials showed mercury separation and failure of Bhasma Pareeksha, whereas Gorvara Puta and Muffle Furnace Puta at 220–230°C produced a light brown, soft product satisfying Rekhapurnatva, Varitara, and Unnama tests. From 470.1 g of Chakrikas, 56.8 g of final product was obtained. **Conclusion:** Repeated Bhavana followed by controlled Puta at 220–230°C yielded a pharmaceutically acceptable Arbudahara Rasa exhibiting classical Bhasma characteristics. The study establishes a reproducible pharmaceutical protocol for the preparation of Arbudahara Rasa.

KEYWORDS: Arbudahara Rasa, Parada Shodhana, Bhavana, Gorvara Puta, Muffle Furnace.

INTRODUCTION

Rasashastra represents an important discipline of Ayurveda that focuses on the purification, processing, and therapeutic application of metals, minerals, and herbo-mineral formulations. These preparations are widely recognized for their potent pharmacological actions and unique pharmaceutical properties. Among the various Rasoushadhis, formulations containing processed mercury (Parada) hold a significant place owing to their extensive therapeutic utility and Yogavahi nature.^[1]

Arbudahara Rasa^[4] is a classical mercurial formulation described in *Rasaratna Samuccaya* (24/135). The formulation is prepared using Shuddha Parada subjected to repeated processing with Tanduliyaka (*Amaranthus spinosus* Linn.), Varshabhu (*Trianthema portulacastrum* Linn.), Tambula (*Piper betel* Linn.), Kumari (*Aloe barbadensis* Linn.), Bala (*Sida cordifolia* Linn.), and Gomutra. Classical texts recommend repeated Bhavana with these media followed by Puta Samskara to obtain the final therapeutic product.

Bhavana is considered a vital pharmaceutical procedure in Ayurvedic drug manufacturing. Continuous trituration with herbal media promotes particle size reduction, improves uniformity, and facilitates the adsorption of bioactive phytoconstituents onto the processed material. Likewise, Puta Samskara induces physicochemical transformations through controlled heating, thereby enhancing the stability and therapeutic suitability of the formulation.

In recent years, increasing emphasis has been placed on the scientific validation and standardization of traditional Ayurvedic medicines. Comprehensive documentation of pharmaceutical procedures and analytical evaluation is therefore necessary to establish quality control parameters and ensure reproducibility. With this perspective, the present study was undertaken to prepare Arbudahara Rasa according to classical Ayurvedic guidelines and to assess its pharmaceutical, physicochemical, and analytical characteristics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of Data

Classical Ayurvedic texts, Rasashastra treatises, and relevant scientific publications were reviewed.

Procurement and Authentication

Raw materials were procured from reliable sources and authenticated by the Departments of Rasa Shastra & Bhaishajya Kalpana and Dravyaguna Vijnana, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru.

Place of Study

Pharmaceutical preparation was carried out at the Teaching Pharmacy, Department of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru.

Ingredients of Arbudahara Rasa

Ingredient	Botanical/Chemical Name
Shuddha Parada ^[1]	Hydrargyrum
Tanduliyaka ^[5]	Amaranthus spinosus Linn.
Varshabhu ^[6]	Trianthema portulacastrum Linn.
Tambula ^[7]	Piper betel Linn.
Kumari ^[8]	Aloe barbadensis Linn.
Bala ^[9]	Sida cordifolia Linn.
Gomutra ^[10]	Cow's urine

Pharmaceutical Procedures

1. Parada Shodhana by Urdhwapatana^[1]
2. Sequential Bhavana with six prescribed media^[4]
3. Repetition of Bhavana cycle.
4. Preparation of Chakrikas.
5. Marana through controlled Puta.

RESULTS

Parada Shodhana

Parameter	Value
Initial Ashuddha Parada	750 g
Final Shuddha Parada	665 g
Yield	91.06%
Loss	85 g

Observations During Shodhana

- Mercury globules progressively reduced during Mardana.
- Complete incorporation into Kalka occurred after 24 hours.
- Purified mercury deposited on the upper pot after Urdhwapatana.
- Maximum lower pot temperature reached approximately 704°C.

Bhavana Observations

Repeated Bhavana gradually reduced the particle size of mercury.

During the first cycle, homogeneous mixing was not observed.

After the second cycle, a thick homogeneous Kalka without visible mercury globules was obtained.

Final Bhavita Kalka Characteristics

- Thick consistency
- Absence of characteristic odour
- No visible mercury globules
- Uniform homogeneous texture
- Crack-free Chakrika formation

Putra Trials**Trial 1 and Trial 2 (Laghu Putra)**

- Mercury separation observed.
- Uneven burning of Chakrikas.
- Failed Bhasma Pareeksha.

Trial 3 (Gorvara Putra)

Parameter	Observation
Maximum temperature	230°C
Mercury separation	Absent
Burning pattern	Uniform
Rekhapurnatva	Positive
Varitara	Positive
Unnama	Positive

Trial 4: (Muffle Furnace).

Parameter	Observation
Temperature	220–230°C
Mercury separation	Absent
Texture	Soft
Color	Brown
Bhasma Pareeksha	Positive

Batch-wise Yield

Batch	Initial Weight (g)	Final Weight (g)
1	109.5	12.6
2	80.4	9.5
3	132.5	16.0
4	76.3	10.4

Final Yield

Parameter	Value
Total weight before Putra	470.1 g
Final product obtained	56.8 g
Total loss	413.3 g

DISCUSSION

The present investigation successfully standardized and documented the pharmaceutical preparation of Arbudahara Rasa in accordance with classical Rasashastra guidelines. The purification of Parada through the Urdhwapatana method was found to be effective, yielding a recovery of 91.06%, which indicates minimal material loss during processing and efficient separation of impurities.

Successive Bhavana procedures with various herbal media played a significant role in the pharmaceutical transformation of the formulation. Initial trituration facilitated reduction in the size of mercury particles, while subsequent Bhavana cycles promoted uniform distribution and complete amalgamation of the ingredients. The bioactive constituents present in Tanduliyaka, Punarnava, Tambula, Kumari, and Bala may have aided the adsorption, stabilization, and integration of mercury within the formulation matrix.

Evaluation of different heating techniques revealed notable differences in the quality of the final product. Laghu Putra was insufficient to achieve the desired transformation, as indicated by separation of mercury and unsatisfactory performance in classical Bhasma Pareeksha tests. In contrast, Gorvara Putra provided gradual and sustained heating, resulting in a product that fulfilled the classical quality parameters. Comparable observations obtained using a muffle furnace suggest that a controlled temperature range of approximately 220–230°C can effectively simulate traditional Putra conditions.

The reduction in weight observed after repeated Putra procedures may be attributed to evaporation of moisture, decomposition of organic constituents, and progressive conversion of the material into a fine incinerated form. The attainment of positive Rekhapurnatva, Varitaratva, and Unnama further confirms adequate particle size reduction and successful completion of the pharmaceutical process.

CONCLUSION

Arbudahara Rasa was successfully prepared following the method described in Rasaratna Samuccaya. The Urdhwapatana process proved effective in achieving purification of Parada, while repeated Bhavana with selected herbal media facilitated proper homogenization and pharmaceutical transformation of the formulation. Controlled heating through Gorvara Putra and muffle furnace techniques within the temperature range of 220–230°C produced a pharmaceutically stable product that satisfied classical Bhasma Pareeksha criteria. The

findings of the present study provide a reproducible pharmaceutical protocol and contribute toward the standardization of Arbudahara Rasa¹¹. This work may serve as a foundation for future analytical, experimental, and clinical investigations aimed at establishing its therapeutic potential.

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